

1 **X-ray computed microtomography characterizes the wound effect that causes sap**
2 **flow underestimation by thermal dissipation sensors**

3 Running head: Characterization of TD sensor wounding by X-ray microCT

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24

25 Research Article

26 **Abstract**

27 Insertion of thermal dissipation (TD) sap flow sensors in living tree stems causes
28 damage of the wood tissue, as is the case with other invasive methods. The subsequent
29 wound formation is one of the main causes of underestimation of tree water use
30 measured by TD sensors. However, the specific alterations in wood anatomy in
31 response to inserted sensors have not yet been characterized, and the linked
32 dysfunctions in xylem conductance and sensor accuracy are still unknown. In this study,
33 we investigate the anatomical mechanisms prompting sap flow underestimation and the
34 dynamic process of wound formation. Successive sets of TD sensors were installed in
35 the early, mid- and end stage of the growing season in diffuse- and ring-porous trees,
36 *Fagus sylvatica* (Linnaeus) and *Quercus petraea* ((Mattuschka) Lieblein), respectively.
37 The trees were cut in autumn and additional sensors were installed in the cut stem
38 segments as controls without wound formation. The wounded area and volume
39 surrounding each sensor was then visually determined by X-ray computed
40 microtomography (X-ray microCT). This technique allowed the characterization of
41 vessel anatomical transformations such as tyloses formation, their spatial distribution
42 and quantification of reduction in conductive area. MicroCT scans showed considerable
43 formation of tyloses that reduced the conductive area of vessels surrounding the inserted
44 TD probes, thus causing an underestimation in sap flux density (SFD) both in beech and
45 oak. Discolored wood tissue was ellipsoidal, larger in the radial plane, more extensive
46 in beech than in oak, and also for sensors installed for longer times. However, the
47 severity of anatomical transformations did not always follow this pattern. Increased
48 wound size with time, for example, did not result in larger SFD underestimation. This
49 information helps to better understand the mechanisms involved in wound effects with
50 TD sensors and allows providing practical recommendations to reduce biases associated
51 with wounding in field sap flow measurements.

52 **Keywords:** Compartmentalization, Discoloration, Embolism, Granier method, Heat
53 transfer, Sap velocity, Sensor bias, Wood anatomy, Wound formation.

54

55 1. Introduction

56 Sap flow sensors are very useful for the assessment of the dynamic response of tree
57 transpiration to changes in environmental variables (i.e.: Loustau et al. 1998, Ewers and
58 Oren 2000, Granier et al. 2000, Fiora and Cescatti 2006) but also to obtain absolute
59 estimates of tree transpiration at stand level (Herbst et al. 2007, 2008, Oishi et al. 2010,
60 Clausnitzer et al. 2011, Gebauer et al. 2012, Ringgaard et al. 2012). Most of the sap flux
61 density methods, such as thermal dissipation (TD), heat field deformation (HFD), heat
62 pulse velocity (HPV), Tmax, heat ratio (HR), or Sapflow+, require the insertion of
63 probes within the tree stem (Swanson and Whitfield 1981, Granier 1985, Burgess et al.
64 2001, Čermák et al. 2004, Davis et al. 2012, Nadezhdina et al. 2012, Vandegehuchte
65 and Steppe 2012, 2013), causing immediate physical damage of the wood tissue and,
66 likely, a subsequent isolating reaction. Several studies suggest that the wound formation
67 may compromise the accuracy of sap flux estimates (Swanson and Whitfield 1981,
68 Smith and Allen 1996, Moore et al. 2010, Steppe et al. 2010, Wullschleger et al. 2011,
69 Vandegehuchte and Steppe 2013, Steppe et al. 2015) due to changes in the anatomical
70 and physical properties of the sapwood that surrounds the inserted sensors. The wound
71 effect was nonetheless only widely recognized for the HPV method (Swanson and
72 Whitfield 1981), but recent studies show that the wound effect represents one of the
73 largest sources of underestimation also for the TD method (Wiedemann et al. 2016),
74 which is one of the most widespread sap flow techniques due to low costs and easily
75 comprehensible sensor construction (Davis et al. 2012). However, anatomical
76 mechanisms that cause systematic underestimations of invasive sap flow sensors have
77 barely been assessed, and are unknown for the TD method in particular.

78
79 The wood tissue undergoes a series of transformations in response to an injury. More
80 specifically, two phases can be discriminated according to their origin and timing of
81 occurrence. The first phase is the direct and immediate physical damage in the adjacent
82 area to the injury. Insertion of sap flow probes within the sapwood causes such a
83 disturbance of conductive tissues surrounding the measurement point. Vessel rupture,
84 consequent air embolism and interruption of water flow around the drilled holes
85 (Dujesiefken et al. 1999) may cause an unavoidable measurement error inherent to all
86 invasive sap flow sensors (Wullschleger et al. 2011). This error is however accounted
87 for when the method is calibrated under similar conditions. More problematic is the

88 indirect effect, occurring later on, associated with wound reaction close to the damaged
89 area. This reaction was already described by the principle of Compartmentalization Of
90 Damage In Trees (CODIT, Shigo 1984, Liese and Dujesiefken 1996, Dujesiefken et al.
91 2005). During the healing process, damaged sapwood tissue is actively isolated from
92 healthy one by sealing the conductive elements and form components in order to
93 prevent embolism, the spread of pathogens, and reduce water loss in the surrounding
94 vessels (Shigo 1979). This process is called compartmentalization and the reaction zone
95 surrounding the wound, detectable as a discoloration of sapwood, is characterized by
96 anatomical changes such as tylose formation, thickening of the xylem cell walls, and
97 phenols or gels accumulation (Rioux et al. 1998, Sun et al. 2006). Accumulation of
98 occluding substances can indeed obstruct extensively the conductive vessels in some
99 species (Rioux et al. 1998, De Micco et al. 2016), reducing considerably the conductive
100 capacity of the affected tissue (Dimond et al. 1955). The use of TD sensors to measure
101 sap flow not only implies drilling holes in the stem, but also application of a permanent
102 source of heat in one of the two probes (Granier 1985). Both are causes of disturbance
103 in the wood tissue that can lead to a compartmentalization reaction and subsequent
104 changes in wood anatomy. A reduction of the conductive capacity of vessels and direct
105 changes in wood porosity, composition and density may alter the heat transport in the
106 wood tissue surrounding the inserted probes.

107

108 The extent of physical and anatomical transformations of the wounded tissue has been
109 previously linked to a proportional reduction in sensor performance (Barrett et al. 1995,
110 Green et al. 2003, Wullschleger et al. 2011). However, very little is known about the
111 nature of occluding elements, their spatial extension and the temporal dynamics of their
112 development. Wound formation has been observed in response to inserted heat pulse
113 velocity (HPV) sensors, where the extension increased with probe thickness and time
114 after installation (Swanson and Whitfield 1981, Barret et al. 1995, Smith and Allen
115 1996, Green et al. 2003). Tree wounding reaction is an active defense mechanism of
116 living trees that involves hormone production and biochemical reactions (Shigo 1984).
117 Therefore, a progressive increase in wound size and more severe biochemical and
118 anatomical transformations are expected with time until the damaged tissue is
119 completely compartmentalized (Swanson and Whitfield 1981, Smith and Allen 1996,
120 Sun et al. 2006). Nonetheless, other factors such as tree growth rate, tree age,
121 phenological status, sensor location and climatic conditions can also determine the

122 compartmentalization rate and the extension of wounded wood tissue in response to
123 injuries (Dimond et al. 1955, Shortle et al. 1996, Dujesiefken et al. 1999, 2005, Sun et
124 al. 2006, Moore et al. 2010, Copini et al. 2014b). For instance, the compartmentalization
125 reaction is faster and wounds extend less when injuries are formed early in the growing
126 season (Dujesiefken et al. 1999, 2005) at warmer temperatures (Shibata et al. 1981,
127 Moore et al. 2010), in young (Shortle et al. 1996) and fast growing trees (Dujesiefken et
128 al. 2005) and in the apical part of the trunk (Sun et al. 2006). Analyses of wounded
129 wood tissue in response to other injuries (e.g. boreholes, pruning, insect outbreaks, etc.)
130 have also shown the formation of a compartmentalized area of variable extension and
131 shape according to the size and characteristics of the injury (Dujesiefken et al. 1999,
132 Copini et al. 2014a). Nonetheless, spatial and temporal details of wound formation
133 associated with TD sensor installation and use are nonexistent.

134

135 Species with different hydraulic architecture may also show contrasting wound
136 reactions (Biggs 1987, Saitoh et al. 1993, Barret et al. 1995). When sapwood is
137 perforated for sensor installation, air comes into the damaged vessels due to the under-
138 pressure existent inside. Wider vessels in ring-porous species are more vulnerable to
139 cavitation, pathogens invasion and less efficient in embolism repair compared to
140 diffuse-porous species (Liese & Dujesiefken 1996, [Dujesiefken et al. 2005](#), Moore et al.
141 2010). The spatial arrangement of vessels in the sapwood will also determine the
142 number of damaged vessels by drilling (Green et al. 1988, Dye et al. 1996). In order to
143 prevent pathogen colonization and further embolism in the injured area, irreversibly
144 cavitated vessels undergo a series of anatomical transformations (Zimmermann 1979,
145 [Cochard & Tyree 1990, Dujesiefken et al. 1999](#)). Accordingly, more severe wound
146 reactions in response to injuries, evidenced by a higher wound closure, extension of
147 discoloration and soluble phenol content, have been found in oak (ring-porous species)
148 compared to beech (diffuse-porous species) (Dujesiefken et al. 2005). Larger wound
149 extension and more severe anatomical transformations may constitute a key explanatory
150 mechanism for the higher sap flow underestimations reported in ring-porous compared
151 to diffuse-porous species (Green et al. 1988, Bush et al. 2010). There are however no
152 precedent studies establishing an empirical relation between wound extension and
153 severity of vessel occlusions and the correspondent species-specific TD sensor bias.

154

155 Knowledge on anatomical mechanisms that underlie wound effect underestimation is
156 therefore the next step towards more accurate sap flux estimates with TD and other
157 invasive sap flow sensors. Here, we investigate the anatomical transformations of wood
158 tissue in response to inserted TD probes up to vessel level, and relate these to the
159 reduction in sensor accuracy. Specifically, we determine geometry and extension of the
160 wounded wood tissue according to the time of wounding and application of a constant
161 source of heat in two tree species with different xylem anatomy: ring-porous oak
162 (*Quercus petraea* (Mattuschka) Lieblein) and diffuse-porous beech (*Fagus sylvatica*
163 Linnaeus) trees. Scanning the wounded wood tissues with X-ray computed
164 microtomography (X-ray microCT) also allowed reconstruction of the 3-D internal
165 microstructure of the xylem vessels to characterize anatomical transformations
166 occurring inside the conductive vessels. Specifically, the microCT technique provided
167 quantification of the tylose-forming capacity, as proportion of occluded vessels, and the
168 severity of these anomalies, as the proportion of vessel lumen occluded. We
169 hypothesize the formation of larger wounds around sensors that have been inserted for
170 longer times into living stems and in association to heated sensor probes, and more
171 severe anatomical changes in ring-porous trees compared to diffuse-porous trees. We
172 also expect to observe a direct relation between the extension of wound anatomical
173 transformations and bias of the respective sap flow sensor.

174

175 **2 Methods**

176 *2.1 Plant material*

177 Study trees were located in a mixed deciduous forest (Leinefelde, Thüringen, Germany,
178 51° 20' 13'' N, 10° 22' 07'' E, and 450 m a.s.l.). Climate in the study area is
179 subatlantic-submontane with an annual mean temperature of 8.2 °C and an annual mean
180 precipitation of 577 mm (2003-2014, O. Kolle, Max Planck Institute for
181 Biogeochemistry, Jena, Germany, personal communication). The forest is relatively
182 homogenous and composed by even-aged stands with European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*
183 L.) as the dominant species (97% of relative abundance) accompanied by sessile oak
184 (*Quercus petraea* (Matt.) Liebl., 3%). Tree height and diameter at breast height were 33
185 m (standard deviation: 7.2 m) and 44 cm (standard deviation: 12.4 cm), respectively
186 (2012, M. Mund, Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, Jena, Germany, personal
187 communication).

188

189 Two beech trees (diffuse-porous) and two oak trees (ring-porous) were selected for this
 190 experiment so that the anatomical changes associated with wound formation around
 191 inserted sap flow sensors could be investigated in two different xylem anatomies. Trees
 192 with regular concentric growth, no evidences of knots, scars, diseases, or irregularities
 193 in the stem surface were chosen.

194

195 *2.2 Thermal dissipation method*

196 The thermal dissipation (TD) sensors were constructed according to Davis et al. (2012)
 197 and specifications of the original design of Granier (1985) (see Wiedemann et al. (2016)
 198 for further details). Each sensor consisted of two stainless steel needles of 20 mm in
 199 length and 1.1 mm in diameter and a T-type thermocouple (copper-constantan). The
 200 upper probe of each sensor was continuously heated at constant power (0.2 W) whereas
 201 the lower probe measured the ambient temperature of the wood. The constantan ends of
 202 the two thermocouples were connected to measure the temperature difference (ΔT)
 203 between the probes. The temperature difference was measured every 60 s and the
 204 average of 10 min was recorded on a data-logger (CR1000, Campbell Scientific, Logan,
 205 UT, USA) and two multiplexers (AM16/32, Campbell Scientific, Logan, UT, USA).

206

207 ΔT is then related to sap flux density (SFD, $\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) using the empirical equation
 208 developed by Granier (1985):

$$209 \quad \text{SFD} = 0.0119 * K^{1.231} \quad (1)$$

210 where 0.0119 and 1.231 are empirically determined coefficients and K is a
 211 dimensionless value defined as:

$$212 \quad K = \frac{\Delta T_0 - \Delta T}{\Delta T} \quad (2)$$

213 ΔT is the measured temperature difference between the two needles at a given sap flux
 214 density. ΔT_0 is the value of ΔT obtained under zero flow conditions or the maximum
 215 temperature difference. The custom-built sensors were previously tested against
 216 commercially available sensors (Type SF-, Ecomatik, Germany) in order to prove their
 217 accuracy and reliability.

218

219 *2.3 Field experimental setup*

220 Six sets of TD sensors were installed at each different date in the growing season (DOY

221 134, 208 and 253; spring, summer and fall sensors, respectively) and in each of the
222 selected trees in the field. Sensors were equally distributed in two 80-cm long stem
223 segments located at two heights (0.9-1.7 m and 2.2-3 m from the base), Hence, each
224 stem height contained three sensors per sampling date located at predefined positions
225 around the stems, so that each state of wound development would be present along the
226 circumference. A minimal horizontal distance of 20 cm and vertical distance of 40 cm
227 was maintained between consecutive sensors, and vertical alignment was avoided to
228 prevent thermal interference. Stem diameters at sensor positions ranged from 31.4 cm to
229 34.1 cm for beech and from 35.3 cm to 39.2 cm for oak (see Wiedemann et al. 2016 for
230 further details).

231 For sensor insertion, a small section of the bark was carefully removed and two holes of
232 2 mm diameter, 2 cm deep and 10 cm apart were drilled radially into the sapwood. A
233 template was used in order to minimize displacement errors during installation. Once
234 the holes were drilled, an aluminum tube of 2 mm diameter with 0.2 mm wall thickness
235 was inserted into each hole so that it was tightly fitted and completely immersed into the
236 sapwood. Sensor probes were then inserted into each corresponding aluminum tube,
237 which was previously filled with silicon grease to increase thermal conductivity.
238 Finally, sensors were protected from physical damages and outdoor conditions and trees
239 were wrapped with aluminum foil to minimize potential natural temperature gradient
240 effects (Do and Rocheteau 2002a, Lubczynski et al. 2012).

241

242 Trees were logged just before the end of the growing season (DOY 287), i.e. 22, 11 and
243 5 weeks after installation of spring, summer and fall sensors, respectively. The TD
244 sensors were removed before logging to avoid any damage, while the aluminum tubes
245 remained inserted in the stems. Two 80-cm long sections of each stem, including the
246 aluminum tubes of all installation dates, were cut, wrapped in plastic foil to prevent
247 desiccation, and carefully transported to the laboratory.

248

249 *2.4 Laboratory sap flux density measurements with gravimetric reference*

250 Details on the calibration of the TD sensors can be found in Wiedemann et al. (2016).
251 Summarizing, once in the laboratory, transversal surfaces of stem segments were treated
252 to reopen the blocked vessels and additional TD sensors (i.e., after cutting, AC) were
253 installed following the procedure described above. These measuring points are

254 considered as reference sensor measurements since the wound reaction is an active
255 mechanism of defense that involves hormone production and biochemical reactions
256 (Shigo 1984), so it is not expected to occur in cut stem segments. Existing holes were
257 equipped again with randomly chosen TD sensors in order to avoid any potential sensor
258 bias. Therefore, each segment contained a total of 12 sensors (3 sensors \times (3 sampling
259 dates + 1 AC)).

260 A sap flow calibration test enabled to compare SFD measured by sensors installed in
261 living trees (i.e., with wound compartmentalization reaction: spring, summer, fall
262 sensors) to the freshly installed AC sensors without wound compartmentalization.
263 Constant pressures were applied through the segments, resulting in a SFD of 0 to
264 $25 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (gravimetric reference). This range is within the magnitude reported
265 in the literature (Granier 1985, Steppe et al. 2010) and previously observed in the field
266 by sensor measurements. The gravimetric SFD, considered as reference, was calculated
267 from the rate of change in mass of water collected and normalized for conducting
268 sapwood area (see Wiedemann et al. 2016 for further details).

269

270 *2.5 Wood sample scans*

271 Following the laboratory measurements, a rectangular prism of 3 x 5 x 2 cm
272 (W x H x L) of the wood tissue surrounding the point of insertion of each sensor probe
273 (heated and non heated probes from each wound age) was cut. Wood sample dimension
274 was chosen *a priori* based on previous estimations of the extent of wound
275 compartmentalization reaction (Sun et al. 2006, Swanson and Whitfield 1981,
276 Wullschleger et al. 2011). Wood samples were subsequently divided along the
277 longitudinal and tangential axes and the internal radial and transverse surfaces were
278 photographed with a portable scanner (CanoScan LiDE 210 Color Image, Canon). The
279 extension of discolored area around the probe insertion was quantified with the image-
280 processing software Fiji (Schindelin et al. 2012). Samples were subsequently stored at -
281 $18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for further analyses.

282 A subset of six wood samples per species was selected and analyzed by X-ray microCT
283 at the Laboratory of Wood Technology (Woodlab-UGent, Belgium). One sample of
284 wood tissue adjacent to the heated probes per wound age was randomly chosen, as well
285 as an additional wood sample adjacent to non heated probes for spring and AC samples.
286 Wood samples were scanned using the multi-resolution X-ray tomography scanner

287 Nanowood (Dierick et al. 2010, Dierick et al. 2014). This scanner is custom built at the
288 UGCT (Ghent University Center of Expertise for X-ray Computed Tomography,
289 www.ugct.ugent.be) in collaboration with the company XRE (www.xre.be). Samples
290 were first scanned at 20 μm in both wet and dry conditions (oven-dried samples at 40°C
291 during 48 hours) to determine the volume and shape of the compartmentalized area.
292 Wet samples were most suitable for visualization of the imprint (i.e. marked or
293 delimited area of compartmentalized tissue likely affected by vessel occlusion with
294 tyloses and/or gels) associated with wound formation, although this was only visible in
295 beech X-ray scans (see Results). Next, the dry wood samples with the oldest wounds
296 (spring) and non-wounded control samples (AC) were scanned at 4 μm resolution for
297 oak and at 1.5 μm resolution for beech. For that, smaller rectangular prisms of 4 x 4 x
298 6.6 mm (W x H x L) were cut at increasing and consecutive distances from the drilled
299 holes in longitudinal and tangential direction. That allowed characterizing the
300 anatomical transformations caused by probe insertion at the vessel level (Steppe et al.
301 2004) while enabling a 3D view inside the vessels.

302

303 *2.6 Image processing of X-ray microCT scans*

304 After image acquisition, microCT serial slices (2D transverse cross-sections) of each
305 intact wood sample were virtually reconstructed to a single 3D stack rendering with the
306 software package Octopus 8.7 (Dierick et al. 2004, Vlassenbroeck et al. 2007), licensed
307 by the spin-off company InsideMatters (www.insidematters.eu). The volume and 3D
308 shape of wounded tissue was determined from the 20 μm 3D stacks of the beech dry
309 wood samples using the Measure Stack plugin (Bob Dougherty, OptiNav Inc.) of the
310 open source image-processing package Fiji (Schindelin et al. 2012). The high-resolution
311 3D X-ray microCT scans of the wood samples were further analyzed to quantify the
312 proportion of occluded vessels and the reduction in conductive lumen area associated
313 with wound formation. This allowed relating TD sap flow underestimation to the
314 intensity of wood anatomical transformations. The image preparation and analyses were
315 performed with the image-processing package Fiji according to the following workflow
316 steps (Fig. 1):

317

318 1) 3D stacks were cropped to exclude irregular margins resulting from the wood sample
319 excision or drilled holes. 2) A Gaussian convolution filter ($\sigma=2$) was used to

320 smooth the 2D slide images and facilitate vessel edge detection. 3) The 2D slide images
321 were then converted to binary wood-air images by using the iterative IsoData algorithm
322 (auto threshold, Ridler and Calvard 1978). 4) In order to quantify vessels accurately,
323 cracks, crunched tissue in the surrounding of the drill hole and late wood pores were
324 filled using the particle analyzer Biovoxxel Toolbox plugin (Jan Borchert/Biovoxxel,
325 www.biovoxxel.de) by establishing an aspect ratio filter > 1 and particle size threshold
326 between 800 and 15,000 pixels for oak and between 400 and 15,000 pixels for beech. 5)
327 Adjacent vessels were then separated using watershed segmentation and their edges
328 smoothed by iteratively minimizing the variance of edge-to-center distance. 6) The
329 convex hull of each vessel was consecutively computed and used to fill remaining
330 vessel edge irregularities. 7) After correct identification of vessels and application of the
331 resulting mask to the original, gaussian-smoothed image stack, the (x, y) position, area,
332 modal grey value and shape descriptors of each vessel were obtained with the particle
333 analyzer plugin. 8) Next, tyloses were detected by setting an empirical, species-specific
334 threshold according to the deviation of the modal grey value within vessels in each 2D
335 slide, so that lower grey values than this threshold allowed to select the tylose-free
336 vessel area. This modal grey threshold was determined by validating results with the
337 visual identification of tyloses in multiple 2D slide images, and then used for the
338 automated identification of tyloses in all 2D slide images of each 3D stack. Similarly as
339 before, the tylose-free area of each vessel was quantified with the particle analyzer
340 plugin, so that the transverse cross-sectional area of tyloses was calculated as the
341 difference between the total vessel area (step 7) and tylose-free vessel area (step 8). The
342 same procedure was also performed in AC samples in order to account for the residual
343 image noise and for any tyloses that may be naturally present in the wood tissue even
344 without wound reaction. 9) Finally, the area fraction of tyloses within each vessel was
345 calculated as the tylose area over total vessel area. Likewise, the proportion of vessels
346 with tyloses in each 2D slide image was determined.

347

348 *2.7 Statistical analyses*

349 Linear regressions were fitted to the gravimetric sap flux density values and the
350 corresponding sensor records for each date of installation and tree species (see
351 Wiedemann et al. 2016 for further details). The effect of the date of sensor installation
352 and the tree species on the relationship between TD sensor SFD estimates and

353 gravimetric values were tested using analyses of covariance (ANCOVA) with
354 “species” or “date of installation” as fixed factors and the gravimetric sap flux as the
355 covariate. Data were root-transformed to improve normality and homoscedasticity
356 (Quinn and Keough 2009). Effects of species, date of probe insertion and heat applied
357 to the probes on the extent of discolored area of the wood samples was tested using
358 multifactor ANOVA tests. Likewise, data were previously transformed when required
359 to achieve normality and homoscedasticity. Statistical analyses were performed with
360 JMP Pro 11.0 software (SAS Institute). Throughout the paper, mean values are followed
361 by ± 1 standard error.

362

363 **3 Results**

364 *3.1 Discolored wood tissue area*

365 The wood tissue area surrounding the point of sensor insertion showed visual symptoms
366 of wound formation and compartmentalization reaction in both species. This was visible
367 by a clear discoloration of the wounded tissue (Fig. 2). This discoloration was clearly
368 visible when the probes were inserted in living trees (spring, summer and fall sensors),
369 but only a discoloration restricted to the area of the drilled hole was visible when sensor
370 installation was done in cut tree stem segments (AC sensors). The extent of
371 discoloration was one order of magnitude larger in the radial than in the transversal
372 plane of the xylem, and more extensive in beech than in oak (Fig. 3, Table 1). The
373 discolored areas were also larger in older wounds, as is shown by the larger discolored
374 areas for sensors installed in spring, followed by sensors installed in summer and
375 autumn (Fig. 3). Note that the extension of discoloration detected in AC samples
376 corresponds to the area of the drilled holes, exclusively due to the mechanical damage,
377 and not to an active discoloration reaction in the surrounding wood tissue. Heated
378 probes generated a wider discoloration, but the constant heat source did not affect the
379 longitudinal elongation of wounded tissue (Fig. 3, Table 1). In addition, there were no
380 significant differences in the extension of the discolored area between the downstream
381 and upstream half of the wood samples, meaning that the wounded area was
382 symmetrical in the radial plane as well as in the transverse plane.

383

384 *3.2 Wood anatomical transformations around the inserted sensors*

385 An elliptical imprint of up to 20 x 29 x 5 mm approx. (longitudinal x radial x tangential)
386 around the inserted probes was clearly visible in beech wood on the 20 µm resolution
387 microCT scans (Fig. 4), when the sensors were installed in living trees (i.e., spring,
388 summer and fall wound-affected samples). Imprints were not visible around the sensors
389 installed in cut beech stems (i.e., wound-free AC samples). However, imprints were not
390 visible in any of the oak scans, although tyloses were already visible occluding oak
391 vessels at 20 µm resolution (Fig. 5). The imprints in beech were delimited and the
392 compartmentalized volume quantified. The shape was symmetrical in radial and
393 transversal planes (Fig. 4) and the volume was larger in older wounds and in wood
394 affected by the heating probes (Fig. 6), confirming the visually observed discoloration
395 patterns (Fig. 3).

396

397 X-ray microCT scans at 4 µm and 1.5 µm resolution for oak and beech, respectively,
398 allowed us to visualize the anatomical transformations in response to wounding both in
399 oak and beech. When sensors were inserted in living trees, tyloses were formed inside
400 the conductive vessels (Fig. 7), interrupting sap flow in the area close to the sensor
401 insertion. Tyloses were not present in vessels of AC wood samples.

402

403 *3.3 Estimation of the span of wood anatomical transformations*

404 The maximum tylose-forming capacity, calculated as the percentage of vessels with
405 tyloses within 1 mm distance from the sensor probe both in the longitudinal and
406 tangential direction was $61.18 \pm 8.77\%$ and $64.58 \pm 2.75\%$ for spring samples of beech
407 and oak, respectively (Fig. 8). This corresponded with a reduction in vessel lumen area
408 of $10.34 \pm 1.30\%$ and $8.13 \pm 0.30\%$, respectively. In oak samples, wood anatomical
409 transformations extended more than 20 mm from the point of probe insertion in the
410 longitudinal direction, as was shown by the high and near constant presence of tyloses
411 along the whole length of the scanned sample. However, the presence of tyloses was
412 more restricted in the tangential direction, with a progressive decline up to 15 mm from
413 the point of probe insertion in number of vessels containing tyloses (up to 10 %
414 approx.) and in vessel area covered by tyloses (up to 3% approx.). In the case of oak,
415 the spatial arrangement of wood anatomical transformations therefore coincided with
416 the elliptical shape of the discoloration (Fig. 3). By contrast, in beech samples, the
417 presence of tyloses showed a progressive and similar decline both in the longitudinal
418 and tangential direction from the point of probe insertion, with less than ca. 20% of

419 vessels with tyloses and ca. 5% of vessel area covered at a distance of ca. 8 mm from
420 the probes.

421

422 *3.4 Sap flux density underestimation by thermal dissipation sensors*

423 Freshly installed AC sensors in beech were able to detect the highest proportion of the
424 gravimetric flux (mean of $86.1\% \pm 5.7\%$), whereas spring ($72.0\% \pm 4.7\%$), summer
425 ($61.8\% \pm 3.9\%$) and fall sensors ($58.0\% \pm 5.0\%$) underestimated the reference
426 gravimetric SFD values in similar magnitudes (Fig. 9a). Differences between AC
427 sensors and sensors installed in living trees (spring, summer, fall) were significant
428 (ANCOVA, $P = 0.0002$). Similar patterns were obtained in the case of oak (Fig. 2b),
429 where AC sensors were able to detect a higher (ANCOVA, $P = 0.0015$) proportion of
430 the flux density ($72.0\% \pm 7.8\%$), compared to spring ($40.0\% \pm 5.1\%$), summer ($52.6\% \pm$
431 10.5%), and fall sensors ($30.8\% \pm 6.1\%$). Sensors installed in living trees also showed
432 similar underestimation of the reference gravimetric SFD values (Fig. 9b). Nonetheless,
433 only two stem segments could be tested in oak, which explains the lower accuracy also
434 shown by AC sensors, low correlation coefficients with the reference gravimetric flux
435 density, larger intercepts and higher errors for the linear regression parameters.

436

437 Wound-affected sensors showed lower SFD underestimations in beech compared to
438 oak, although differences were statistically marginal and with a significant interaction
439 of species with the gravimetric flux density (ANCOVA, $P = 0.046$). Wound-free AC
440 sensors had a similar performance in both beech and oak (ANCOVA, $P = 0.55$) with no
441 significant interactions.

442

443 **4. Discussion**

444 Sap flux density measurements are systematically underestimated by sensors that are
445 inserted in living tree stems (Swanson and Whitfield 1981, Steppe et al. 2010,
446 Wiedemann et al. 2016). The wound formation in the living wood tissue that surrounds
447 the inserted sensor probes has been previously suggested as a possible cause. However,
448 hardly any information was available on the anatomical transformations occurring in the
449 conductive sapwood in response to wounding and its impact on the accuracy of SFD
450 estimates. Our results confirm that the damage resulting from drilling holes in living
451 trees to install the TD sensors, and likely any other invasive sap flow sensor, activate

452 the wound compartmentalization reaction. We detected the formation of occluding
453 elements such as tyloses and most likely gels inside the vessels surrounding the inserted
454 probes. The vessel occlusion in this area is unequivocally associated to considerable sap
455 flow underestimations by TD sensors. Characterization of wood anatomical and
456 physiological responses to the inserted sap flow sensors and assessment of their
457 functional significance allowed us to design specific recommendations to improve the
458 accuracy of field SFD estimates.

459

460 *4.1 Wound-associated anatomical transformations*

461 X-ray microCT scans revealed extensive formation of tyloses inside the conductive
462 vessels adjacent to the inserted sap flow sensors (Fig. 7). Tyloses are balloon-like
463 swellings or projections from ray cells, and to a much lesser extent from axial
464 paratracheal parenchyma cells, of xylem that grow into the lumen of adjacent vessels
465 through bordered pits (Zimmermann 1979, Shigo 1991, Pearce 1996, Sun et al. 2008).
466 When vessels are air-filled due to freezing, drought stress or injuries, tyloses intrude
467 from adjacent cells and occlude the vascular tissue to prevent further damage to the
468 plant (Dimond et al. 1955, Aleemullah and Walsh 1996, Parke et al. 2007, Collins et al.
469 2009, McElrone et al. 2010). Most recent studies point to vessel embolism as a single
470 direct trigger (Rioux et al. 1998, De Micco et al. 2016) despite that the primary stimuli
471 for vessel occlusion in response to injuries is still controversial. Tyloses may, in any
472 case, exert an effective control of pathogen entry from outside and prevent systematic
473 migration (Sun et al. 2006, De Micco et al. 2016).

474 Tyloses are initially composed by starch and a suberized primary wall layer, which
475 allows tissue impermeabilization by impeding fluid penetration into the vessel
476 (Parameswaran et al. 1985). Once tyloses reach their maximum expansion, they can
477 develop a secondary wall and nucleus, becoming real cells connected to the vessel-
478 associated cells across pits, although nucleus and nucleolus may disappear progressively
479 with age (Zimmermann 1979). At this stage, a multilayered cell wall deposition of
480 suberin or lignification of the tyloses secondary wall can form sclerified tyloses. More
481 specifically, *Fagus* and *Quercus* form suberised tyloses (Schmitt and Liese 1993),
482 which certainly contribute to further constrain water transport (Dimond 1955,
483 Parameswaran et al. 1985, Schmitt and Liese 1993, Parke et al. 2007, Collins et al.
484 2009).

485

486 Other occluding substances can also appear during the compartmentalization reaction in
487 association with tyloses. Increased concentrations of phenols in the compartmentalized
488 tissue act as antibiotics, preventing the pathogens' infection in the area close to the
489 injury (Rioux et al. 1998). Parenchyma cells and tyloses also secrete pectic substances
490 and other polysaccharides (so-called "gels" (Rioux et al. 1998) or "gums" in previous
491 literature). Pectin is then dispersed along with the remaining sap movement and it
492 aggregates and swells after impregnation with water still remaining in the vessels. Gels
493 may function as a cement of tyloses and also keep the parenchyma cells adjacent to the
494 occluded vessels hydrated (Rioux et al. 1998). This soluble occluding material that
495 appears early in diseased or injured plants is frequently observed in fresh sections as a
496 translucent and grey area that becomes darker and as solid gum deposit in later
497 wounding stages. Discoloration of living xylem cells may also result from the oxidation
498 of phenols to produce melanoid pigments, which may eventually become trapped in
499 occluding gels in vessels together with dark colored mycelium of fungi infecting the
500 damaged area (Shigo 1979, Dimond et al. 1955, Rioux et al. 1998). Gel expansion in
501 contact with the remaining capillary water may have played a more predominant role in
502 beech vessels due to their smaller size ($1909.5 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}^2$ in beech and $45890 \pm 50 \mu\text{m}^2$ in
503 oak) and higher density (96.51 ± 0.18 vessels mm^{-2} and 2.794 ± 0.007 vessels mm^{-2} ,
504 respectively). This mechanism may actually explain the clear imprints that were visible
505 in microCT scans of wet beech samples (Fig. 4) and their absence in oak (Fig. 5). Even
506 that these imprints cannot be unequivocally associated to accumulation of gels in this
507 study, the presence of tyloses inside conductive vessels can clearly be distinguished in
508 the microCT scans, which most probably plays a role in the reduction of SFD in the
509 zone around the TD sensors.

510

511 Little is known about the formation of tyloses in response to sensor insertion and its
512 implications on measured SFD. Tylose-forming capacity, estimated as the percentage of
513 vessels with tyloses within 20 mm of the drilled hole, was very high in both study
514 species. Up to ca. 61% and 65% of the conductive vessels were occluded by tyloses
515 within 1 mm distance of the sensor probe both in the longitudinal and tangential
516 directions in beech and oak, respectively (Fig. 8c and d). Tylose presence was
517 generalized inside most of the conductive vessels and along a considerable length, but
518 vessel lumen area was only reduced by up to 10% and 8% in beech and oak,

519 respectively (Fig. 8a and b). Presence of tyloses thus disturbs considerably the flow path
520 and heat conductivity in the conductive tissue around the sensors, resulting in a
521 significant reduction in sensor accuracy. Actually, the active formation of tyloses in
522 living tree stems, probably together with accumulation of gels that takes place during
523 compartmentalization, caused a $21.4 \pm 3\%$ and $47.5 \pm 3.8\%$ underestimation in SFD by
524 TD sensors installed in living beech and oak trees, respectively (Fig. 9, see Wiedemann
525 et al. 2016 for further details). Nonetheless, differences between SFD underestimations
526 detected for beech and oak were not statistically significant, neither the tylose-forming
527 capacity and severity of tyloses occlusions within the closest 1 mm from the probes,
528 which impede us to establish a direct relation between species-specific differences in
529 wounding reaction and SFD underestimations.

530

531 *4.2 Shape and span of wounded tissue*

532 A clearly visible discolored area surrounded the probes inserted in living trees, whereas
533 discoloration did not occur around the sensors installed in the cut stems (Fig. 2). This
534 change in wood color is a clear symptom of wound development in response to an
535 injury (Shigo 1979). The span of discoloration around the probes was one order of
536 magnitude larger in the radial than in the transverse plane (Fig. 3) and was symmetrical,
537 resulting in an ellipsoidal area for both species, similar to Barret et al. (1995). This was
538 consistent with the volume of compartmentalized tissue detected in X-ray microCT
539 scans of beech samples (Fig. 4) and with the tylose-forming capacity and severity along
540 the longitudinal and tangential directions in the case of oak (Fig. 8b, d). Air bubbles,
541 fungi spores and bacteria can invade vessels damaged by drilling the holes and travel
542 along the conducts along the longitudinal direction. The active sealing of air-filled
543 vessels to prevent the spread of pathogens and/or further embolism (Pearce 1991,
544 Clerivet et al. 2000, Sun et al. 2006, De Micco et al. 2016) resulted in an ellipsoidal
545 compartmentalized area. Likewise, cylindrical increment borers (usually ranging
546 between 4.00 to 5.15 mm diameter) have been reported to also cause wounds that were
547 more extended in the longitudinal direction (length of 16-155 cm) (Dujesiefken et al.
548 1999). However, wounds generated in response to insertion of cylindrical heat pulse
549 velocity probes have been assumed to be cylindrical in other studies (Swanson et al.
550 1981, Wullschleger et al. 2011). Since wounds are the result of an active
551 compartmentalization reaction of injured tissue, wound extension will be directly

552 related to the size and shape of these injuries but exacerbated in the sap flow direction,
553 thus resulting in more extended wound reaction in the longitudinal direction.

554

555 The span of wounded tissue in the conductive xylem has been previously linked to a
556 direct reduction in sap flow sensor performance (Barrett et al. 1995, Wullschleger et al.
557 2011). In our study, wound sizes were several orders of magnitude larger than wounds
558 associated with heat pulse probes of similar dimensions: $777 \pm 63 \text{ mm}^2$ and 292 ± 33
559 mm^2 in the radial plane for beech and oak (Fig. 3) compared to 4-15 mm^2 reported in
560 Wullschleger et al. (2011), and this was true even for non-heated probes. Wound width
561 also increased in constantly heated TD probes (Fig. 3 and 6). In contrast, HPV probes
562 are only heated intermittently during a few seconds. This fact and overlooking the wider
563 extension of wounds in the radial plane and increasing wound sizes with time since
564 HPV probe insertion could partly explain the large differences in wound sizes between
565 these two invasive sap flow methods. Since we did not find a direct relationship
566 between wound extension and the magnitude of SFD underestimations, larger wound
567 sizes in TD sensors can hence not explain completely the larger SFD underestimations
568 compared to other sap flow methods (Steppe et al. 2010).

569

570 Our study tree species showed differences between the discoloration extension and
571 anatomical alterations. Discolorations were ellipsoidal in both species but longer in
572 beech samples (Fig. 3). On the contrary, tyloses extended similarly in the longitudinal
573 and tangential direction in beech (Fig. 8a, c) but more in the longitudinal direction in
574 oak (Fig. 8b, d). Therefore, the span of wood anatomical transformations does not
575 necessarily coincide with discolored gel-occluded areas. Pectic material in vessel
576 lumina can actually originate from both the tyloses primary wall (Meyer and Côté 1968,
577 Ouellette 1980, Bensen and Kučera 1990, Rioux et al. 1998) or directly from the
578 protective layer of xylem parenchyma cells (Bensen and Kučera 1990, Rioux et al.
579 1998). Different species may also have divergent mechanisms to ensure an effective
580 isolation of the damaged tissue by forming prominently either tyloses or gels (Biggs
581 1987, Bensen and Kučera 1990, Schmitt and Liese 1990, Saitoh et al. 1993, Rioux et al.
582 1998, De Micco et al. 2016). Although both oak and beech are tylose and gel-forming
583 species (Von Aufsess 1984, Schwarze and Baum 2000, InsideWood database 2004-
584 onwards, Wheeler 2011), our results suggest that gel production may be more tightly
585 associated to tylose production in oak, where the geometry of discolorations and tyloses

586 coincide. In contrast in beech, parenchyma cells may produce additional pectic material
587 at further distances from the drilled holes to complete the isolation. Despite the fact that
588 no significant differences were detected between SFD underestimations between the
589 two study species (Wiedemann et al. 2016, Fig. 9), different wound sizes and wounding
590 mechanisms point to species-dependent wound effects on SFD estimates.

591

592 *4.3 Time frame for wound development*

593 Wounds showed a progressive development up to 22 weeks after sensor insertion in
594 living stems. This is shown by the increasing trend in extension of discolored tissue,
595 particularly in the radial plane (Fig. 3, Table 1) and in the volume of compartmentalized
596 area in beech (Fig. 6) with the time span of sensor installation in the living tree stem. A
597 faster and more efficient compartmentalization has been described for the early growing
598 season, when physiological mechanisms involved in defense and prevention of
599 pathogen infections are fully active and increased activity of parenchyma cells allow a
600 more efficient formation of accessory substances (Dujesiefken et al. 1999, 2005).
601 Higher temperatures may also facilitate a faster wound reaction, increasing the
602 efficiency of tissue compartmentalization (Shibata et al. 1981, Moore et al. 2010).
603 Production of occluding elements may differ along the year with tyloses forming
604 predominantly in summer and gels in winter (Sun et al. 2008). According to our results,
605 the time span in which sensors have been inserted into the living wood tissue is even
606 more determining for wound size than the tree phenological status or temperature.

607

608 Wounds were already present in the autumn wood samples, which were sampled five
609 weeks after sensor insertion. This period is consistent with the time span for wound
610 development reported in other studies, e.g. 14-21 days in Smith and Allen (1996), 10-20
611 days in Swanson and Whitfield (1981), and 7 days after pruning in Sun et al. (2006).
612 We have shown in an earlier study (Wiedemann et al. 2016) that field SFD values
613 decreased immediately after sensor installation and reached stable values after about 2
614 weeks, which was interpreted as an indication for the time frame of the exhibition of the
615 wound effect symptoms. This time frame should be, nonetheless, considered as a first
616 orientation to demarcate potential wound-affected measurements, since the rate of
617 wound compartmentalization reaction might be influenced by several factors such as
618 tree phenological status, climatic conditions, age, growth rate, and sensor location
619 (Liese and Dujesiefken 1996, Shortle et al. 1996, Dujesiefken et al. 1999, 2005, Sun et

620 al. 2006, Moore et al. 2010). To mention some examples, young trees (Shortle et al.
621 1996), and in general trees with fast growth rates (Dujesiefken et al. 2005), are related
622 to faster injury repair. Tylose development is also much slower in latewood and at the
623 base than in the apical region (Sun et al. 2006). Interestingly, older and larger wounds
624 did not result in larger SFD underestimations by TD sensors (Fig. 9). Sensor accuracy
625 may be only sensitive to physical and anatomical transformations in a restricted area
626 close to the sensors. Given the high tylose-forming capacity within the closest
627 millimeters from the sensor probes (Fig. 8c, d), even early wounding reactions in this
628 area are sufficient to result in substantial SFD underestimations.

629

630 *4.4 Recommendations to improve the accuracy of the TD method in the field*

631 Most of the sap flow methods require insertion of probes into the living tree stem,
632 which makes them potentially vulnerable to wound-effect bias. This effect is widely
633 recognized for the heat pulse velocity method with specific mathematical corrections
634 available (Swanson et al. 1981). The TD method is, however, based on empirical
635 equations and does not include physical and thermal properties of the wood (Lu et al.
636 2004), which makes it difficult to implement a correction using a similar approach. Our
637 results suggest that wound development is species-specific, which might translate into
638 species-specific SFD underestimations despite it could not be detected here (cf.
639 Wiedemann et al. 2016). Many other factors can also influence time and magnitude of
640 the wound effect (Shortle et al. 1996, Dujesiefken et al. 1999, 2005, Moore et al. 2010,
641 Wiedemann et al. 2016), which makes application of a general empirical correction to
642 field sap flux data questionable. A laboratory calibration for each particular case is, on
643 the other hand, very laborious and in most cases not feasible due to logistic reasons or
644 lack of infrastructure (Steppe et al. 2015).

645 Some preventive measures can be suggested in order to reduce the
646 compartmentalization reaction and tyloses formation near the inserted probes. Drilling
647 the holes carefully at predawn or under overcast meteorological conditions could help to
648 minimize the disruption of the xylem (Lu et al 2004). A reduced sensor size or the use
649 of chemical inhibitors of tyloses formation (Sun et al. 2007, McElrone et al. 2010) may
650 also contribute to minimize wound-derived bias. Nonetheless, these last two measures
651 may require new calibrations (James et al. 2002) or involve side alterations in hydraulic
652 conductivity, and none of these measures would completely avoid wound formation and

653 hence sap flow underestimation. As is explained in detail in Wiedemann et al. (2016), a
654 field comparison between SFD measured by recently installed sensors, and hence
655 without wound development, and sensors installed in the previous four weeks, hence
656 with developed wounds (Swanson and Whitfield 1981, Smith and Allen 1996), allows
657 to determine the time frame for wound development and, therefore, calculate a
658 correction for SFD underestimation caused by wound formation. Moreover, similar
659 underestimations regardless the extension of wounds at different stages of development
660 also imply that wound-derived underestimations are unavoidable 2-4 weeks after sensor
661 installation (Wiedemann et al. 2016). The accuracy of sap flow measurements would be
662 then compromised as soon as wounds start to develop around the inserted probes. The
663 suggested practical approach in Wiedemann et al. (2016) will also offer valuable
664 information about factors influencing the magnitude of the wound effect in each
665 particular case. In the long term, the obtained information could be incorporated into
666 numerical models (Wullschleger et al. 2011), so that specific wound corrections can be
667 developed *a priori*.

668

669 **5. Conclusions**

670 Invasive sap flow sensors can considerably underestimate sap flux density due to wound
671 formation around the probes inserted into living tree stems. X-ray microCT scans
672 allowed us to characterize, for the first time, the anatomical transformations happening
673 in wood tissues and relate them to the corresponding bias of TD sensors. As part of an
674 active compartmentalization reaction, considerable formation of tyloses, and most likely
675 the production of gels, occluded the conductive vessels around the inserted TD probes,
676 which reduced hydraulic conductivity in these areas. The occurrence of tyloses was
677 indeed unequivocally associated to a reduction in detected flow by TD sensors. Tyloses
678 occluded most of the conductive vessels in the zone closest to the sensor, although their
679 spatial distribution did not always coincide with the discolored wound area.
680 Discolorations likely associated to fungi infection and presence of dark colored gels
681 (Dimond et al. 1955, Rioux et al. 1998) were ellipsoidal, larger in the radial plane, and
682 differed between species, with wound age and the presence of a heat source. However,
683 larger wound sizes did not lead to higher SFD underestimations.

684

685 Wood anatomical and physiological alterations described here in response to inserted
686 TD sensors may represent one of the main sources of sap flow underestimations in a

687 large proportion of studies worldwide. Wounding occlusions most likely occur in
688 response to any invasive sap flow sensor, since the compartmentalization reaction is
689 common in response to injuries. Moreover, tyloses and other vessel occluding materials
690 have been described in more than 111 and 106 families and subfamilies, respectively,
691 and affect to about 17% and 18% of world forests (InsideWood modern wood database
692 2004-onwards, Wheeler 2011). Both tyloses and solidified gels (gums) in an advanced
693 stage of development, such as the ones present in discolored wound tissues, can be
694 considered as irreversible vessel occlusions, since they would require very complex
695 processes to be degraded (De Micco et al. 2016). Despite its relevance, the use of a
696 universal wound correction factor is probably not advisable (Wiedemann et al. 2016),
697 since the formation of occluding elements is influenced by wound age, tree species, the
698 presence of a heat source as well as by climatic conditions, sensor dimensions and
699 phenology, amongst others. The information provided in our study contributes to detect
700 potential biased sap flow measurements *a priori* and to design strategies to improve the
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719

720 **8. References**

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933 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

934

935 Figure 1: Illustrative scheme on the workflow steps for the image processing of the high
 936 resolution X-ray microCT 3D stacks (4 and 1.5 μm for oak and beech, respectively) to
 937 determine the fraction of vessels with tyloses and the transverse cross-sectional area
 938 fraction of tyloses within vessels on each 2D image slide.

939

940 Figure 2: Example of discoloration surrounding the point of probe insertion in beech a)
 941 and oak c) compared with normal tissue (b and d, respectively). Pictures show the radial
 942 plane, the point of sensor insertion is indicated by white arrows; left is the bark. The
 943 discoloured tissue present in spring samples (a, c) and absent in AC samples (b, d) is an
 944 indicator of the compartmentalization reaction.

945

946 Figure 3: Discoloured area in the transverse and the radial plane of the wood samples
 947 for beech and oak. Diagrams of the transversal and radial planes of the wood samples
 948 are shown at the right hand side of the figure. The X-axes indicate the different periods
 949 when sensors were installed: Spring, Summer and Fall correspond to sensors installed
 950 for 22, 11 and 5 weeks in living stems, respectively. After Cut corresponds to sensors
 951 installed in cut tree stems. The effect of applied heat by the heated probes is also shown.
 952 Different letters above the bars indicate significant differences among dates (Tukey
 953 HSD test after multifactor ANOVA).

954

955 Figure 4: X-ray microCT scans of wood tissue of beech at 20 μm resolution. The
 956 images show the transverse cross-section of the wood tissue surrounding probes
 957 installed in living trees in spring a) and in cut stems (AC, b). All images are taken ca. 2
 958 mm downstream from the probe insertion. The bark is located at the top part of each
 959 image. White arrows point at crushed vessels due to mechanical insertion of the probe
 960 (in both images), blue arrows in the beech spring sample a) point at the imprint of the
 961 compartmentalized area. This imprint was not visible in AC samples.

962

963 Figure 5: X-ray microCT scans of wood tissue of oak at 20 μm resolution. The images
 964 a) and b) show the transverse cross-section of the wood tissue surrounding probes
 965 installed in living trees in spring (a) and in cut stems (AC, b). The bark is located at the
 966 top part of these images. The images c) and d) show the radial and tangential sections of

967 the wood tissue surrounding probes installed in living trees in spring. All images are
 968 taken ca. 2 mm downstream from the probe insertion. White arrows point at crushed
 969 vessels due to mechanical insertion of the probe or the point of the sensor insertion, blue
 970 arrows point to vessels with tyloses.

971

972 Figure 6: Volume of the compartmentalized area as it was visible on the X-ray microCT
 973 scans of beech wood samples at 20 μm resolution. The X-axis indicates the different
 974 periods when sensors were installed. The effect of the applied heat by the heated probes
 975 is also shown.

976

977 Figure 7: X-ray microCT scans of wood tissue of beech (a, c) and oak (b, d) at 1.5 and
 978 4 μm resolution, respectively. The images are transverse cross-sections of the wood
 979 tissue surrounding the probes, which were installed in spring (a, b) and after cutting the
 980 stems (AC; c, d). The images were taken ca. 2 mm downstream from the probe
 981 insertion. The approximate location of the images is shown in the corresponding 20 μm
 982 scan (small image below the spring samples). White arrows point at tyloses that
 983 partially occluded the vessels of the conductive xylem in both species. Tyloses were not
 984 observed in AC samples (c, d).

985

986 Figure 8: Extent of the anatomical transformations from the point of probe insertion (0
 987 mm from the hole) along the longitudinal and tangential direction of the beech (a, c) and
 988 oak (b, d) wood tissue. In a) and b) points represent the percentage of vessel lumen area
 989 covered by tyloses in each transversal slide. In c) and d) each point represents the
 990 percentage of vessels partially or totally clogged by tyloses in each transversal slide of
 991 the wood sample. Bars represent the standard errors from 50 consecutive slides.
 992 Diagrams of the longitudinal and tangential directions of the wood samples are shown at
 993 the right. The smallest vessel considered was ca. 0.001 mm^2 for beech and 0.01 mm^2 for
 994 oak.

995

996 Figure 9: Underestimation of sap flux density by TD sensors determined by lab
 997 calibration. Graphs show the comparison of SFD measured by TD sensors and the
 998 corresponding gravimetric reference values in a) beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L., diffuse-
 999 porous species) and b) oak (*Quercus petraea* Liebl., ring-porous species). Markers
 1000 represent the average values for one calibration step (34-108 sensor readings averaged

1001 per data point), including standard errors of the TD sensors and the gravimetric
1002 measurements. Solid lines are linear fits while the dashed line is the 1:1 relation.
1003 Coloured areas represent the 95% confidence intervals of the linear regressions.
1004 Redrawn from Wiedemann et al. (2016).